

SHERLOCK

Supporting the energy transition of the building stock

D4.1 SHERLOCK's programmes contents, teaching aids, and guidelines

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D4.1 SHERLOCK's programmes contents, teaching aids, and guidelines	
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Project overview

SHERLOCK aims to contribute to the EU's decarbonisation targets by co-designing with stakeholders a MOOC-based micromaster programme and a VET-oriented short training course based on microcredentials and case study education, targeting students and professionals from both the building energy retrofitting and financial sectors. The project will help overcome the skills mismatch between financial operators and project developers to foster the acceleration of building energy retrofitting across Europe.

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Executive summary

Deliverable D4.1 of the SHERLOCK project presents the development of educational programmes designed to address the skills gap in the building energy retrofitting and financial sectors. It outlines the development of two primary educational offerings: a MOOC-based micro-master programme and a Vocational Education and Training (VET) short course, both of which rely on micro-credentials to deliver targeted, stackable knowledge. The micro-master programme consists of 15 micro-credentials, each comprising 3 European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits, for a total of 30 ECTS across the entire programme. These micro-credentials are divided into two tailored curricula, each addressing different professional needs:

- Technical professionals in the building sector, focusing on engineering, architecture, and energy management.
- Financial professionals, focusing on green finance, energy governance, and economic models for energy efficiency.

Each micro-credential is designed as a 3 ECTS self-contained learning module, allowing learners to build expertise in specific areas such as energy auditing, energy performance contracting, business models for energy efficiency, and green infrastructure finance. Learners can complete individual micro-credentials or combine them to earn the micro-master, which provides a comprehensive skill set for managing energy-efficient renovation projects. The modular structure allows professionals to earn a certification for each micro-credential, accumulating recognized credentials as they progress through the programme. The Vocational Education and Training (VET) programme complements this by offering a series of short, practical courses tailored for vocational trainers and professionals in the construction and energy sectors.

A key feature of the SHERLOCK project is the co-creation approach used to develop these programmes. Extensive collaboration with stakeholders, including industry professionals, educators, and learners, has ensured that the micro-credentials address real-world skills gaps. The project conducted surveys and workshops across seven countries—Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, and Spain—to gather input from over 160 stakeholders. This data was essential in shaping the content of the micro-credentials and aligning them with current industry needs, particularly in the building energy and financial sectors.

The BoostMySkills MOOC platform, an integral part of SHERLOCK's delivery system, is a state-of-the-art online learning environment that hosts the micro-credentials and micro-master programme. The platform supports a self-paced learning model, allowing learners to enrol in over 60 open-access MCs created

in the framework of several EU-projects. Progress is continuously monitored, and learners receive digital micro-credentials upon completing each course. These micro-credentials can be shared on professional networks such as LinkedIn, enhancing career prospects and professional recognition. Professionals can accumulate multiple micro-credentials to demonstrate their expertise in key areas, with the option to earn a micro-master certification once they complete all required modules. This model allows learners to build a portfolio of verified skills over time, making it easier to adapt to industry changes and remain competitive in the job market.

The present report describes SHERLOCK's educational programmes, outlining their learning objectives, contents, materials and features implemented in the MOOC platform. Moreover, it summarises the stakeholders' co-creation approach implemented by SHERLOCK for identifying the educational needs and skills gaps in the building sector.

1 Introduction

The SHERLOCK project aims at addressing the pressing need for specialized skills in the building energy retrofitting and financial sectors. With Europe's ambitious decarbonization targets, there is a growing demand for skilled professionals who can effectively bridge the gap between project developers, engineers, and financial institutions to accelerate energy-efficient building renovations across the continent. SHERLOCK seeks to fill this skills gap through the co-creation of innovative, flexible educational programmes that target both students and professionals.

The SHERLOCK project revolves around the creation of two major educational pathways: a MOOC-based micro-master programme and a VET-oriented short training course, both developed with a strong emphasis on micro-credentials. Micro-credentials offer a revolutionary approach to education, providing bite-sized, stackable learning modules that can be tailored to the specific needs of learners and industries [1]. These modules are designed to be practical, targeted, and industry-relevant, aligning perfectly with the rapid pace of technological advancements and evolving industry requirements. In today's competitive job market, where skills quickly become outdated, SHERLOCK's micro-credential framework offers a dynamic, flexible solution for continuous upskilling and reskilling [2].

The micro-credentials themselves are designed to be stackable, meaning learners can accumulate several micro-credentials over time, gradually building a comprehensive portfolio of validated expertise [3]. This flexible approach not only provides learners with verifiable proof of their skills but also allows employers to identify candidates with the specific competencies needed for their projects. By aligning with the EU guidelines on micro-credentials [1], SHERLOCK ensures that these educational achievements are recognized across Europe, making them highly valuable in the global job market.

The MOOC-based micro-master programme developed within SHERLOCK is designed to target professionals in both the technical and financial sectors, with the aim of providing them with the necessary skills to facilitate energy-efficient building renovations. This programme is structured around 15 carefully selected micro-credentials, each covering a specific area of expertise within the field of energy renovation. The curriculum spans topics such as energy auditing, energy-efficient business models, communication strategies with financial institutions, and renewable energy integration. The micro-credentials can be combined to form a full micro-master programme, which offers a holistic understanding of both the technical and financial aspects of energy retrofitting projects.

In parallel, SHERLOCK has also developed a Vocational Education and Training (VET) programme aimed at equipping vocational trainers and professionals with

the tools to upskill workers in the energy renovation sector [4]. The VET programme focuses on practical, hands-on training, with an emphasis on teaching techniques that integrate real-world scenarios and case studies. This approach ensures that the knowledge and skills gained are directly applicable to the workplace, enabling workers to quickly adapt to new technologies and energy-efficient practices. The VET programme is structured around specific micro-credentials that address core topics such as energy efficiency, project management, and green financing. By offering a flexible, modular approach to education, the SHERLOCK VET programme allows learners to tailor their training to their individual needs and career goals.

Central to the success of the SHERLOCK educational framework is the co-creation methodology employed in the development of the micro-credentials and programmes [5,6]. Co-creation involves close collaboration between SHERLOCK's consortium partners, industry stakeholders, educators, and learners. This participatory approach ensures that the educational content is aligned with the real-world needs of the energy and financial sectors. Stakeholder engagement activities such as workshops, interviews, and surveys were conducted in multiple countries, including Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, and Spain. These activities provided valuable insights into the current knowledge gaps and skills requirements in the energy renovation market, allowing SHERLOCK to design a curriculum that addresses the most pressing challenges faced by the industry [7].

Deliverable D4.1 focuses on the content development, teaching aids, and guidelines necessary to implement these educational programmes. It outlines the methodologies and processes employed in the creation of SHERLOCK's micro-credentials, which include collaboration with key stakeholders from the building energy and financial sectors. Through co-creation workshops, surveys, and direct interaction with industry experts, SHERLOCK has developed educational content that is both relevant and practical, ensuring that learners acquire the skills needed to thrive in their professions.

It also details the digital infrastructure supporting the SHERLOCK educational programmes. The BoostMySkills MOOC platform, developed as part of the SHERLOCK project, is a state-of-the-art online learning environment that hosts the micro-credentials and micro-master programmes. This platform is designed to offer a seamless learning experience, allowing users to access course materials, monitor their progress, and interact with peers and instructors. The platform's features include video lectures, interactive exercises, quizzes, and final assessments, all of which are designed to engage learners and ensure mastery of the material. Additionally, learners can earn digital certificates and micro-credentials upon completing each course, which can be shared on professional platforms such as LinkedIn, enhancing their career prospects.

2 SHERLOCK micro-credential approach

2.1 Pillars

In today's fast-paced, technology-driven world, the traditional model of education is undergoing a profound transformation, shaped by the growing demand for more personalized, flexible, and relevant knowledge acquisition methods. As learners increasingly seek alternatives to conventional educational paths, Micro Programmes, built on the foundation of Micro Credentials, have emerged as a powerful solution to deliver specialized knowledge effectively and efficiently. These targeted, bite-sized learning modules offer a revolutionary approach to education that aligns with the needs of modern learners and the evolving demands of various industries. Micro-based learning represents a significant shift in the educational and training landscape, providing a personalized experience that caters to diverse learning styles and preferences. In a rapidly evolving job market where skills quickly become outdated, Micro Programmes offer a highly adaptable framework for continuous upskilling and reskilling. By addressing specific skill gaps and providing industry-aligned content, these programs allow learners to stay competitive and relevant in their fields. The main pillars for the development of micro-credentials, in line with the European Commission guidelines [1], adopted by SHERLOCK are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 SHERLOCK pillars in creating micro-credentials

Pillars	Description
Targeted and Relevant Learning	Micro Credentials are often designed in collaboration with industry experts, ensuring that the skills are directly applicable to current industry demands. This relevance helps bridge the gap between traditional education and real-world application, also making MCs a valuable resource for employers.
Flexible, On-Demand Learning	A major benefit of micro-credentials is their flexibility. Learners can access these courses anytime, anywhere, from any device with internet access. This on-demand model is perfect for busy professionals, students, and lifelong learners, allowing them to seamlessly integrate education into their schedules. With micro programs, learners can choose when and how to learn, completing courses at their own pace.
Customised Learning Paths	Micro-credentials offer customization, enabling learners to tailor their learning experiences to their specific needs and goals. With a broad selection of micro courses available, learners can design personalized learning paths that align with their career aspirations or areas of interest. This adaptability ensures learners focus on the most relevant topics, enhancing their understanding and skillset.

Pillars	Description
Continuous Learning and Skill Building	In today's fast-changing job market, staying up to date is crucial for career growth. Micro-credentials support continuous learning, offering short, focused lessons that can easily fit into a busy professional's routine. These programs enable learners to enhance their skills and stay competitive without the need for long-term commitments to traditional education.
Stackability	Micro-credentials offer verifiable proof of skill development. Learners can accumulate multiple micro credentials over time, building a portfolio of validated expertise. This stacking approach helps learners demonstrate mastery in various areas, making them more attractive to employers and clients looking for specialized knowledge. Furthermore, MCs can be combined to form Micro-programmes tailored on a specific discipline or sector.
Engaging Learning Experience	Micro credentials can employ interactive learning tools like videos, quizzes, and simulations to create engaging experiences fostering retention and leading to a more effective and enjoyable learning journey. This interactive design keeps learners motivated and enhances, while also creates new learning opportunities.
Cost-effectiveness	Compared to traditional higher education, micro programs are generally more affordable and accessible. Learners only pay for the specific courses they need, which makes education more budget friendly. Additionally, the shorter duration of these programs allows learners to quickly see returns on their investment through improved skills and employability.
Rapid Adaptation to Industry Needs	Micro credentials are agile, easily adjusting to the latest industry trends and technologies. As new skills and practices emerge, micro programs can be rapidly developed and deployed, providing learners with up-to-date knowledge. This responsiveness ensures that learners are always equipped with the most relevant skills for their field.
Boosting Motivation and Confidence	The brief duration of micro courses gives learners a sense of accomplishment upon completion, encouraging continued learning. As they accumulate micro credentials, learners gain confidence in their growing expertise, while achievements and recognitions motivate further learning and skill development.
Accessibility	Micro credentials are digital and borderless, giving learners access to expertise from across the globe. Whether taught by leading professionals, renowned academics, or industry experts, these courses bring diverse perspectives, enriching the learning experience and broadening learners' knowledge.

2.2 Co-creation approach

Since the continuous assessment of educational needs and identification of knowledge gaps is a key step in developing user-centred educational program, SHERLOCK employs co-creation [4] to collaboratively design and deliver innovative educational solutions with the active participation of relevant stakeholders [5]. Therefore, SHERLOCK developed a multi-faceted methodology (Figure 1) that includes systematic data collection, skills extraction using Generative AI, topic modelling, and direct interactions with stakeholders through tailored surveys, interviews, and local stakeholder meetings.

Figure 1: Sherlock co-creation framework for Micro-credentials

2.3 Summary of the result from the stakeholders' interaction

The SHERLOCK framework employs a co-creation process involving job market analysis and input from seven national knowledge centres to meet key objectives in the building renovation sector. First, it identifies educational needs and knowledge gaps to ensure relevant training content. These needs are then translated into specific learning objectives for a targeted micro-credential basket, aligning content with practical industry skills.

Finally, the micro-credentials undergo a thorough validation process, incorporating feedback from industry stakeholders, educators, and learners to confirm alignment with industry standards and address initial knowledge gaps effectively.

2.3.1 SHERLOCK's surveys

SHERLOCK project's survey targeted a broad range of stakeholders - including industry professionals, students, and professors - to gather insights on preferred learning formats, necessary knowledge levels, and the relevance of energy efficiency topics for micro-credential courses.

Out of 162 responses, the majority came from professionals (55%), followed by students (34%) and professors (11%), with a notable representation from STEM fields (71%) and SSH fields (29%). The survey revealed key areas of interest, including the fundamentals of energy efficiency in buildings, renewables integration, and the circularity of energy practices, scoring between 60-70 on a 0-100 relevance scale. Most respondents expected an intermediate to advanced level of expertise from the courses, emphasizing practical application over theoretical knowledge.

Preferences for training formats showed a clear preference for hybrid learning (62%), with 24% favouring fully virtual and 14% opting for in-person sessions. Webinars, practical training, and hybrid lectures were the most preferred learning modes, while micro-learning sessions lasting 1-2 hours per week were the favoured time commitment. The strong interest in flexible learning formats underscores the need for courses that accommodate busy schedules and diverse learning preferences.

For VET stakeholders, a secondary survey highlighted similar results. Respondents identified topics like energy efficiency benefits, smart building technologies, funding mechanisms, and project management as essential for skill-building. Motivations included sustainable practices, practical skills development, and career advancement, with a strong preference for hybrid formats and hands-on examples led by professionals.

The surveys have been distributed online; on the website of SHERLOCK, LinkedIn and on the partners' social media accounts.

2.3.2 SHERLOCK co-creation workshops

Complementing the surveys, seven co-creation workshops conducted between February and June 2024 further refined the stakeholder insights. Workshops were held in Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, and Spain, offering in-depth perspectives on knowledge gaps, skill needs, and optimal training formats for energy efficiency courses.

- Participants in Greece emphasised tailored training to address local microclimate conditions and the need for bioclimatic design. Irish participants focused on bridging knowledge gaps in energy modelling, financing, and integration with EU policy. Both regions recommended blended learning formats, emphasizing hands-on and real-world exercises.
- Italian attendees noted the value of shifting from deterministic to probabilistic approaches and the importance of financial training for professionals in energy efficiency. In Lithuania, topics like energy assessment and indoor air quality were prioritized. Both workshops supported hybrid learning with a practical, hands-on approach.
- During the workshops in Portugal, further key topics included renewables integration, heat transfer, and energy certification, with Portuguese participants emphasizing skills in solar integration, building interfaces, and cost estimation. Slovakian attendees identified a need for in-depth energy audits, certifications, and financial contracting education. Both groups recommended blended formats with practical demonstrations and initial in-person sessions to enhance clarity.
- The first SHERLOCK stakeholder workshop took place on the 8th of October, gathering over 60 students and professionals from the energy, building, and financial sectors. This workshop provided a platform to explore the challenges, opportunities, and practical experiences shaping the energy renovation sector across Europe, with a special focus on Slovakia. Following four insightful presentations, a panel discussion was held, covering key topics such as the role of local and national stakeholders in energy renovation, the importance of trust between residents and experts, and the crucial role of education—especially in engaging children and young people—in promoting energy efficiency. The panel welcomed thought-provoking questions from the audience, sparking further discussions on building trust and the need for collaborative efforts in energy retrofitting. The speakers' presentations can be found on the project's website under the "Resources" section.

All workshops consistently advocated for case study education training that allows for a combination of online modules and practical case studies. This format would ensure accessibility while fostering skill development through interactive, real-world examples. The summary of the main recommendations are listed in Table 2

Table 2: Summary of the main recommendations collected during stakeholders' interaction

Recommendation	Description
Focus on Core Topics	Prioritize essential topics like energy efficiency fundamentals, renewable integration, smart building technologies, project management, and financial mechanisms.
Hybrid and Flexible Learning Formats	Implement a blended format combining online modules and practical case studies to accommodate diverse schedules and learning preferences
Tailored Content Delivery	Adjust course content based on audience needs and lecturer expertise, ensuring effective delivery
Develop Comprehensive Resources	Create extensive support materials, such as best practice databases and documentation, to complement training and support practical application.
Enhance Collaboration and Communication	Promote interdisciplinary workshops and stakeholder engagement to build cross-sector knowledge and skills, Involve company experts in the design and delivery of course contents.

The results from the co-creation workshops have also been disseminated on [the website](#) and the project's social media accounts.

2.3.3 Skill identification

Based on data from stakeholder surveys and job data advertisement platforms, a job-market analysis revealed key skills and competences in the financial and building sectors (for a full description, please see SHERLOCK D3,.2). Shared and sector-specific skills with both sectors were identified, highlighting that project management and communication as critical competencies, emphasizing the need for effective communication and the capacity to oversee projects efficiently. In finance, analytical skills are especially important for roles such as financial analysts and investment advisors, given the sector's reliance on data-driven decision-making. Conversely, the building sector prioritizes technical skills essential for understanding construction techniques and operating specialized tools, as well as problem-solving abilities crucial for navigating the complex, dynamic nature of construction projects (Figure 2).

Emerging trends reveal a growing importance of digital literacy and data analysis across both industries, reflecting the influence of technological advancements. Soft skills, including communication and problem-solving, are increasingly vital, as they facilitate collaboration and enhance effective project management. By understanding these skill demands, workforce development initiatives can focus on preparing professionals to meet industry needs, ensuring they remain competitive in an evolving job market.

Figure 2: Comparative analysis between the top 50 skills in the financial and building sector (see SHERLOCK's deliverable D3.2)

3 Micro-credentials development

3.1 Micro-credential selection

Each Micro-Credential (MC) comprises individual, self-contained modules organised in a pyramidal structure (as shown in Figure 3) to cover different knowledge levels—from foundational concepts to specialized topics. The MCs are designed to align with EU standards and are accessible on a MOOC platform within an open-education framework. The approach gives the students both a strong background in a specific area and at the same time a degree of specialisation.

During the initial process each partner were asked to suggest several titles of MCs. This exercise produced more than 50 micro-credential proposals relevant for the building energy renovation sector, which then went under scrutiny by external stakeholders. Following direct interactions with the stakeholders and several national/international surveys, a final basket of 48 MCs has been identified (D3.2)

Figure 3: Pyramidal structure of the individual micro-credential [6]

Starting from the SHERLOCK MCs basket (see D3.2) previously identified, a working group was established to identify and select the 15 most relevant titles based on the knowledge and skill gaps identified. The working group consisted of members of SHERLOCK consortium, including advisory board members, and stakeholder representatives in the field of building energy renovation sector. The result of this activities was a list of 15 Micro-credentials (Table 3).

Table 3: Selected MCs from SHERLOCK MCs basket

#	Title
MC01	Basics of energy efficiency
MC02	Decision making toward sustainable city
MC03	Communication strategies with financial institutions
MC04	Advertising and public relations in the Energy sector
MC05	Systemic Design for Energy Retrofitting
MC06	Energy auditing of buildings
MC07	Incorporation of natural materials in energy renovation of buildings
MC08	Solar process economics
MC09	Circular Economy in the Built Environment
MC10	Energy Consumption in buildings
MC11	Green Infrastructure Finance
MC12	Environmental Social Governance Finance
MC13	Business model for energy efficiency in buildings
MC14	Energy performance contracting of buildings
MC15	Probabilistic Approach for Energy Efficiency Evaluation

3.2 Micro-credential structure creation and content production

Each micro-credential has a size of 3 ECTS and are designed to be delivered in the MOOC platform Boostmyskills. Each course is divided into sections, and each section in subsection which contains a sequence of learning units which may be videos, reading materials, and exercises or marked tests. An example of MC structure is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Generic Micro-credential structure adopted in SHERLOCK

MC name and MC number	Provider	Reviewer name	Date reviewed (dd-mm-yy)						
Section	Length of each section		Type of content	No. of exercise questions, if applicable	Is all content available and working as expected? (includes exercise content, where applicable)	Is all content audible? (if applicable)	How would you rate content? (1 is very poor; 10 is very good)	In your opinion, is this MC ready to go-live to learners?	List issues / comments (please list any issues and the timestamp of the issue in the video - e.g. blurred sound or blurred vision)
	Minutes	Seconds							
Example	10	27			Yes	Yes	10	Yes	
1.1									
1.2									
1.3									
1.4									
1.5									
2.1									
2.2									
2.3									
2.4									
2.5									
2.6									
3.1									
3.2									
3.3									
3.4									

Figure 6: Internal quality test report adopted in SHERLOCK

4 SHERLOCK Micro-Master programme

The selected MCs (Table 3) have been merged in a Micro-Master (MM) programme “*Energy renovation in the building sector*” aimed at equipping professionals in the building and financial sectors with relevant skills and competences to unlock the successful deployment of energy renovation projects in buildings. The MM consists of 10 MCs from the selected basket shown in Table 3, each one of them with a size of 3 ECTS each for a total of 30 ECTS for the entire programme (Figure 7). The Micro-Master programme is divided into two curricula tailored on the needs of two different target audience:

- **Curriculum 1 – technical professionals:** the curriculum aims to equip technical professionals – e.g., engineers, architects, building energy managers, surveyors, etc. – with relevant knowledge, skills and competences in business and management. Main topics of the curriculum are contractual business models, green financings, energy governance, etc., which are complemented with transversal skills such as decision-making tools, communication strategies and public relations.
- **Curriculum 2 – financial/business professionals:** the curriculum aims to equip financial/business professionals – e.g., credit institutions, investors, portfolio managers, etc. – with relevant knowledge, skills and competences in the energy sector. Main topics of the curriculum are building energy consumption, energy auditing, energy efficiency strategies, renewable energies, circular economy and energy renovation strategies etc., which are complemented with transversal skills such as decision-making tools, communication strategies and public relations.

Figure 7: Structure of SHERLOCK Micro-Master programme

As it is possible to note in Figure 7, the two curricula have five MCs in common – which represents the ones covering the transversal skills mentioned above – while other five MCs are specific for each curriculum. The table below reports the overview of the selected MCs as function of the two curricula.

Table 4: List of selected MCs and curricula assignment

#	Title	Curriculum
MC01	Basics of energy efficiency	Both curricula
MC02	Decision making toward sustainable city	Both curricula
MC03	Communication strategies with financial institutions	Both curricula
MC04	Advertising and public relations in the Energy sector	Both curricula
MC05	Systemic Design for Energy Retrofitting	Both curricula
MC06	Energy auditing of buildings	Curriculum 2
MC07	Incorporation of natural materials in energy renovation of buildings	Curriculum 2
MC08	Solar process economics	Curriculum 2
MC09	Circular Economy in the Built Environment	Curriculum 2
MC10	Energy Consumption in buildings	Curriculum 2
MC11	Green Infrastructure Finance	Curriculum 1
MC12	Environmental Social Governance Finance	Curriculum 1
MC13	Business model for energy efficiency in buildings	Curriculum 1
MC14	Energy performance contracting of buildings	Curriculum 1
MC15	Probabilistic Approach for Energy Efficiency Evaluation	Curriculum 1

4.1 Curriculum 1: Building energy renovation financing

The Building Energy Renovation Financing curriculum of the Micro-Master *Energy renovation in the building sector*, tailored for technical professionals in the building energy sector (e.g., engineers, architects, surveyors, building energy managers and facility managers, energy consultants and auditors, project managers, etc.) prepares participants with essential business and management skills needed to lead sustainable energy retrofitting projects. The

course combines technical knowledge with business acumen, emphasizing contractual business models, green financing, and energy governance. In addition to the core technical topics, the course also includes crucial transversal skills such as decision-making tools, effective communication strategies with financial institutions, and public relations techniques. These skills are essential for professionals tasked with managing and implementing energy-efficient retrofitting in buildings to meet the demands of sustainable urban environments.

Table 5: MM02 Energy renovation in the building sector (Building energy renovation financing)

Micro-Master		Energy renovation in the building sector			
Curriculum		<i>Building energy renovation financing</i>			
Course code	MM-01	ECTS	30	MCs numbers	10
Suitable for	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> STEM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NON-STEM	EQF level:		6-7
Target audience					
The course is designed for financial/business professionals – e.g., credit institutions, investors, portfolio managers, etc. – who seek to develop technical skills in the building energy renovation sector.					
Learning objectives					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a foundational understanding of the main economic drivers of building energy renovation projects. • Learn the basics of green infrastructure finance and Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) finance as they relate to sustainable building projects. • Acquire knowledge in business models specific to energy-efficient projects and understand the implications of various contractual arrangements. • Adopt a probabilistic approach for assessing and forecasting energy efficiency improvements and related financial risks. • Evaluate and apply decision-making tools for sustainable urban development. • Gain skills in communicating effectively with financial institutions, stakeholders, and the public regarding energy retrofitting projects. 					
Course content					
MCs #	MCs Title				ECTS
MC01	Basics of energy efficiency				3
MC02	Decision making toward sustainable city				3
MC03	Communication strategies with financial institutions				3
MC04	Advertising and public relations in the Energy sector				3
MC05	Systemic Design for Energy Retrofitting				3
MC11	Green Infrastructure Finance				3
MC12	Environmental Social Governance Finance				3
MC13	Business model for energy efficiency in buildings				3
MC14	Energy performance contracting of buildings				3
MC15	Probabilistic Approach for Energy Efficiency Evaluation				3

4.2 Curriculum 2: Building energy economics

The curriculum Building Energy Economics of the Micro-Master *Energy renovation in the building sector* is designed to provide financial and business professionals—including credit institutions, investors, portfolio managers, and others—with a robust technical foundation in the energy sector, specifically focusing on building retrofitting. Participants will gain an in-depth understanding of energy consumption in buildings, energy auditing practices, energy efficiency improvements, renewable energy integration, and the application of circular economy principles in building renovations. The course aims to enable financial professionals to make informed investment decisions, assess energy-related projects, and communicate effectively with technical experts in the energy field. Additionally, the curriculum integrates transversal skills such as decision-making frameworks, communication strategies, and public relations approaches tailored to the energy and sustainability sectors.

Table 6: MM02 Energy renovation in the building sector (Building energy economics)

Micro-Master	Energy renovation in the building sector		
Curriculum	<i>Building energy economics</i>		
Course code	MM-02	ECTS 30	MCs numbers 10
Suitable for	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> STEM	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NON-STEM	EQF level: 6-7
Target Audience			
The course is designed for professionals in engineering, architecture, and related fields who seek to develop business and management skills for energy-efficient building retrofitting.			
Learning objectives			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To understand the fundamentals of building energy consumption and key drivers of energy efficiency. • To develop skills in energy auditing and recognize indicators for energy-saving opportunities. • To explore and evaluate various energy efficiency and renovation strategies, including renewable energy options and circular economy applications. • To examine decision-making tools for sustainable urban planning and energy retrofitting investments. • To acquire practical skills in communicating and promoting energy projects to stakeholders and the public. • To foster a systemic perspective in design and decision-making for energy retrofitting. 			
Course content			
MCs #	MCs Title	ECTS	
MC01	Basics of energy efficiency	3	
MC02	Decision making toward sustainable city	3	
MC03	Communication strategies with financial institutions	3	

MC04	Advertising and public relations in the Energy sector	3
MC05	Systemic Design for Energy Retrofitting	3
MC06	Energy auditing of buildings	3
MC07	Incorporation of natural materials in energy renovation of buildings	3
MC08	Solar process economics	3
MC09	Circular Economy in Built Environment	3
MC10	Energy Consumption in buildings	3

5 SHERLOCK Vocational programme

Due to the rapidly changing needs in the industrial sector, a continuous training and upskilling of the workforce is necessary. This micro credential is specifically designed for VET (Vocational Education and Training) and professionals who work in the construction and energy sectors and who want to upgrade their skills using innovative methodologies and practical materials relative to their line of work. In this context, SHERLOCK developed a micro-credential, "Energy Efficiency in Buildings for VET Upskilling", specifically designed for VET providers, to equip them with essential knowledge and practical skills to advance energy efficiency practices in the building sector. The course combines theoretical foundations with applied exercises, making it particularly relevant for professionals aiming to integrate energy-efficient and circular economy principles within VET curricula. It covers critical aspects of energy efficiency in building environments and provides insights into funding opportunities, EU policies, and sustainable building practices. Through a combination of interactive learning modules, videos, readings, and multiple-choice assessments, learners will gain a practical understanding of the latest directives, strategies, and tools for promoting energy efficiency in their fields.

Table 7: Sherlock Vocational programme description

Topics	Description
Building energy efficiency	Techniques and principles to reduce energy consumption in buildings to provides insight on insulation, efficient lighting, HVAC systems, and energy management strategies that can be incorporated into training programs. Learners will explore case studies of energy-efficient buildings and analyse methods to minimize energy waste in building.
Renewable energy	VET professionals are introduced to renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal energy. It emphasizes the importance of integrating renewable energy technologies into buildings and training environments, enabling learners to advocate for

Topics	Description
	and implement sustainable power solutions in vocational training projects and curriculums.
Circular economy	Strategies for reducing waste and maximizing resource efficiency, covering sustainable building materials, recycling, and designing for durability. Participants will explore circular economy principles and its incorporation into building construction, to promote a sustainable approach to building design and maintenance.
EU green deal	An overview of the EU Green Deal and its goals for carbon neutrality and sustainable growth is provided to VET professionals who will learn about policies impacting energy use and sustainability in the building sector, as well as how to align their training programs with EU sustainability targets. This understanding helps VET professionals guide their students in preparing for future regulatory and environmental standards.
Energy project financing	Overview of funding options for sustainable building projects and green technology implementation. In this topic, VET professionals will learn about EU and national grants, subsidies, and private financing options. This knowledge empowers VET professionals to support students and institutions in securing funding for energy-efficient projects.
Smart technologies	Smart technologies focus on innovative systems and devices that enhance energy efficiency and user control within buildings. For VET, this includes familiarizing learners with smart thermostats, energy management software, and IoT devices. VET professionals will learn how to integrate these technologies into their training programs, preparing students for the growing demand for smart building skills in the workforce.
Learning objectives	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the fundamental concepts of energy efficiency and recognize its importance within the context of buildings and VET institutions. • Analyse key EU policies and directives on energy efficiency and the circular economy, including the EU Energy Efficiency Directive, EU Green Deal, and Circular Economy Plan. • Apply circular economy principles within building-related practices to promote sustainable construction and resource use. • Identify and access funding opportunities for energy-efficient projects, leveraging EU and national resources for green transformations. • Implement energy-efficient practices in buildings, using techniques suited to vocational training environments. 	

6 SHERLOCK MOOC Platform Boostmyskills

The SHERLOCK project aims to address the critical skills gap in the energy efficiency and building renovation sectors by developing an innovative educational framework based on micro-credentials. To achieve this, the SHERLOCK consortium has created a comprehensive Micro-Master programme and a short training course for professionals and students, which are delivered through the BoostMySkills MOOC platform. This platform has been adapted from a previous project, ensuring its features align with the SHERLOCK programme's needs.

6.1 User interface (UI) of Boostmyskills platform

BoostMySkills is an advanced digital learning platform developed as KER of the Horizon Europe project RES4CITY. It offers a broad spectrum of open educational resources and courses specifically tailored for professionals, students, and anyone with a zeal to elevate their skill set. This platform operates as a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course), offering easily accessible, top-notch educational material across diverse fields including technology, business, sustainability, science, etc. Figure 8 shows the high-level structure of Boostmyskills with reference to RES4CITY programme contents, which is replicated in SHERLOCK.

Figure 8: High-level structure of Boostmyskills platform

The initial page the learner reaches is the intro pages where the first part is shown in Figure 12, which is designed in order to encourage potential learners in enrolling, learning and completing the courses. The button “Register” leads the user to the registration page (Figure 10) where the user can register.

Figure 9: SHERLOCK BoostMySkills homepage - showing the first part of the introduction, objective of the programme and encouragement to participate

Figure 10: SHERLOCK BoostMySkills registration page

The learner can then browse the Boostmyskills micro-credential catalogue which includes all SHERLOCK MCs plus other courses developed in the framework of RES4CITY project. All information of a specific micro-credential is reported in a dedicated page (Figure 13), which includes context and overview, MC content and the indication of the student’s effort. A similar layout is presented for micro-programmes / micro-masters.

The screenshot shows a user interface for a micro-credential. At the top left is a circular icon with a green globe and leaves. To its right is the title 'Circular Economy in the Built Environment' and the creator 'by CECOLAB'. Below the title is a green 'Enrol →' button and social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column has a section header 'Context and Overview' followed by two paragraphs of text. The right column has a light blue box containing course details: 'Course Number: MC09_SHERLOCK_v1' and '15hrs per week for 5 weeks'. Below this is a 'Sections' box with a numbered list of four items: '1 Fundamental concepts', '2 Introduction to the Circular Economy and Sustainable Energy Use', '3 Sustainable Fashion', and '4 FINAL EXAM'.

Figure 13: Example of the micro-credential description page in Boostmyskills (MC09: Circular Economy in the Build Environment)

The learners can enrol in the course by simply clicking the button “Enrol” below the MC title. Following the enrolment, the user can start the micro-credentials (Figure 14) by clicking “Start Course”, which leads to the first activity of the course, which is typically an introductory video (Figure 15). Other type of activities include reading materials, exercises and tests (Figure 16).

Course Progress Dates

Circular Economy in the Built Environment

Begin your course today Start course →

Sections Expand all ▾

- Introduction to Sustainability and the Circular Economy
 - Introduction to Sustainability
 - Introduction to Circular Economy
 - Final Test
- Circular Economy for the Built Environment

Figure 14: MC course content listed inside the MC page following student’s enrolment.

Course Progress Dates

Circular Economy in the Built Environment > Introduction to Sustainability and the Circular Economy > Introduction to Sustainability

1.1 1.2 1.3

Introduction to Sustainability

Introduction to Sustainability

MC09_S1_Sub1_U1_Introduction to Sustainability

Millenium Development Goals (2000-2015)

Watch on YouTube

Figure 15: Example of video lecture inside Boostmyskills.

Circular Economy in the Built Environment > Introduction to Sustainability and the Circular Economy > Introduction to Sustainability

← 1.1 1.2 1.3 →

Exercise 1.1.1
 Bookmark this page

Multiple Choice
 1 point possible (ungraded)

Which sentence best describes the concept of "Sustainable Development"?

- Economic growth based on uncontrolled natural resource consumption without considering future generations
- Population growth based on economic development
- Development capable of meeting the needs of the present without compromising those of future generations
- Development based on reduction of present needs in order to not compromise those of future generations

Submit

< Previous Next >

Figure 16: Example of exercise tab in Boostmyskills

Course Progress Dates

Your progress

Course completion
 This represents how much of the course content you have completed. Note that some content may not yet be released.

19%

Grades
 This represents your weighted grade against the grade needed to pass this course.

0% Your current grade 50%
 Passing grade

▲ A weighted grade of 50% is required to pass in this course

Grade summary ⓘ

Assignment type	Weight	Grade	Weighted grade
Homework ¹	15%	0%	0%
Lab ²	15%	0%	0%
Midterm Exam	30%	0%	0%
Final Exam	40%	0%	0%
Your current weighted grade summary			0%

Figure 17: Example of progress monitoring tab in Boostmyskills

Since self-monitoring progress during a course is crucial, Boostmyskills implement a progress monitoring tool (Figure 17) that allows students to maintain a clear understanding of how much content has been covered and evaluating the current standing in relation to the course's overall requirements. It allows students to stay informed about their completion rates and assess whether they are on track to meet learning objectives.

6.2 Summary of Boostmyskills main features

The BoostMySkills MOOC platform is designed to provide an engaging and interactive learning experience, offering a variety of features that support the educational goals of the SHERLOCK programme. These features ensure that learners can effectively absorb course content while tracking their progress and interacting with both peers and instructors. The following table summarises the main features offered by Boostmyskills platform and embedded in SHERLOCK courses.

Table 8: Summary of the main Boostmyskills features

Feature	Description
Course catalogue	An extensive array of open courses is available on BoostMySkills, each course meticulously detailed with information encompassing the course content, duration, level of difficulty, and user reviews.
Educational resources	The courses are comprised of video lectures, readings, quizzes, and assignments. They also feature interactive components such as forums, peer assessments, and live Q&A sessions
Continuous assessment	Exercises and tests are provided along the entire course to allow learners to continuously test the understanding and competence acquired.
Progress monitoring	Users are provided with tools to monitor their advancement through each course, with the added incentive of receiving a certificate or microcredential upon completion.
Completion certificates	Upon completing all course requirements, learners receive digital certificates of completion, which can be shared on professional platforms such as LinkedIn.
Resource downloads	Learners can access supplementary resources, such as PDF guides, slides, and case studies, for further study.

7 Conclusions

The present report describes SHERLOCK educational programmes which are aimed at addressing the skills gap in the building energy retrofitting and financial sectors. By leveraging a micro-credential approach, SHERLOCK has created a flexible, targeted, and modular educational framework that meets the evolving needs of professionals and learners in these crucial fields. The deliverable has outlined the structured development of programme content, teaching aids, and guidelines that underpin SHERLOCK's aim to foster a skilled workforce capable of driving Europe's decarbonization efforts.

The innovative use of micro-credentials as the foundation for both the MOOC-based micro-master programme and the VET-oriented short training course provides a new paradigm for education in the energy sector. These short, stackable credentials allow learners to gain specific, verifiable skills that can be immediately applied in their professions. Additionally, by offering a flexible learning path, SHERLOCK enables participants from diverse backgrounds—whether in the technical or financial domains—to upskill or reskill at their own pace, making the programme accessible to a wide range of professionals.

The co-creation process, which involved close collaboration with key stakeholders across Europe, has ensured that the curriculum and micro-credentials are aligned with industry demands. Feedback from industry professionals, educators, and learners has been instrumental in shaping the content, ensuring that it is relevant, practical, and immediately applicable in real-world contexts. This engagement with stakeholders also highlighted the need for flexible learning formats, which SHERLOCK has successfully integrated into its programmes. The emphasis on hybrid and online learning formats, supported by the BoostMySkills MOOC platform, ensures that SHERLOCK's educational offerings are not only accessible but also adaptable to the busy schedules of professionals seeking continuous education. BoostMySkills MOOC platform plays a critical role in delivering these educational programmes. Its user-friendly interface, continuous progress monitoring, and interactive learning features ensure a smooth and engaging experience for learners. By offering digital certificates and micro-credentials, the platform enables learners to showcase their skills and achievements, enhancing their employability and professional development opportunities.

Through the development of micro-credentials and the micro-master programme, SHERLOCK is poised to support the European Union's broader objectives of reducing carbon emissions and enhancing energy efficiency across the building sector. By bridging the gap between financial operators and project developers, SHERLOCK fosters a collaborative environment where professionals from both fields can work together to accelerate the retrofitting of Europe's building stock.

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